

Harnessing Tourism Potentials of West African States (Ecowas) in Advancing the Promotion of Tourism

LAWAL, Yazid Ibrahim

Department of Physical & Health Education

Faculty of Education

Bayero University, Kano

ilyazid65@gmail.com

ORCHID: 0009-0007-2669-3000

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17073312>

Abstract

West Africa is a big territory that boasts of a rich history, beautiful scenery, friendly people and a varied geography, extraordinary bio-density, a rich ecological system; extensive history, varied culture and famous for its two features Sahara desert and Niger River. There are fifteen (15) countries that made the region, which are Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, and Togo, all blessed with various tourism destination but untapped. The destination of this paper was the tourism potentials of each state, the opportunities and challenges in advancing the promotion of the tourism potentials of each states and harnessing the tourism destinations of each of the West African States has been identified. The paper concludes that there are weaknesses that are damaging the image of the entire states and to address these challenges thereby promoting and harnessing its tourism competitiveness; an effective promotion of the tourism sector is required through mass media campaign and provision of tourism infrastructure. The paper recommended that there is the need for political will of each State, investment in tourism, potentials, and the importance of respecting and appreciating the roles of partnership between the private and public sectors.

Keywords: Advancing, harnessing, promotion, potentials & Tourism

Introduction

The continent of Africa is such a large landmass categorized into five (5) regions comprising of South Africa, East Africa, West Africa, Equatorial Africa and the African Transition Zone. The focus of this paper is the West African States with fifteen (15) countries; Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone and Togo, all blessed with tourism potentials but untapped (World Travel & Tourism Council, WTTC, 2010). West African States a territory featuring beautiful countries with several hundred million inhabitants and these countries have a rich history, beautiful scenery, friendly people and a varied geography, extra ordinary bio-density, rich ecological system and the region is famous for its two features Sahara desert, Niger River and its extensive history and varied culture (World Travel & Tourism Council, WTTC, 2010). It also boasts of a rich history, beautiful scenery, friendly people, a varied geography, extra ordinary bio-density, rich ecological system; extensive history, varied culture and famous for its two features Sahara desert and Niger River (WTTC, 2010).

Tourism activity is a combination of tourism products like transportation, accommodation, infrastructure, attractions, and support services to form an industry (UNWTO United Nations World Tourism Organization 2018; Melese & Belda, [2021](#)). Tourism is the largest worldwide service-based industry and makes significant contributions to service sector growth and infrastructure development in airports, roads, schools, retail areas and is an activity that combines tourism potentials and the use

of tourism products like transportation, accommodation, infrastructure, attractions and support services to form an industry (Dwyer & Edwards, 2000; Honey, 2009). What makes a city rise above the rest in the hearts of travelers? Is the tourism attractions which are the iconic landmarks and the distinctive culture, the major reason why tourists visit a destination? (Awoseyin, 2006). It is now generally accepted that prerequisites for tourism development are attractions, accommodation, access and without attractions either natural (climate, landscapes, coast, mountains) or man-made (historic sites, theme parks, festivals) tourism cannot develop (African, 2006). Tourism is vital for the success of many economies around the world and there are several benefits of tourism on host destinations, this according to African, (2006) includes:

- i. Tourism boosts the revenue of the economy
- ii. Creates thousands of jobs
- iii. Develops the infrastructures of a country, and
- iv. Plants a sense of cultural exchange between foreigners and citizens

All this require a high standard of accommodation and infrastructure and a good transportation network; the basics for tourism development (African Hospitality, 2006). This paper looked at the number of issues resulting in low attractiveness of West African States as a destination for international tourism that need to be addressed in promotional terms.

Travel and Tourism in West African States

Travel and tourism in the 14 West African states have evolved significantly over time, shaped by cultural heritage, historical events, and economic factors. Historically, tourism focused on cultural sites and natural reserves and is rooted in its rich history, particularly related to the transatlantic slave trade and is a mix of traditional and modern forms of travel with a focus on culture, nature and business (Elite, 2017) Travel and tourism in West African states is conducted in a variety of ways, depending on the country and the destination (Emerald insight, 2019). Some common forms of travel and tourism according to Emerald, (2019) in the region includes:

- i. Many tour companies offer organized group tours to popular destinations in West Africa, these tours include transport, accommodation, guided tours and activities such as safari, cultural tours, and beach excursions.
- ii. Independent travelers can choose to book their own accommodation and transport, and plan their own itinerary. This is a popular option for budget travelers or those who prefer the flexibility and freedom of making their own plans.
- iii. Many organizations offer opportunities for travelers to volunteer in West Africa, often in community development or conservation projects. These programs offer a unique way to experience a country while also contributing to a good cause.
- iv. West African states are home to a number of important international trade hubs, and business travel is common. This type of travel is mostly conducted through conferences, business delegations, and Trade fairs.
- v. West African states are home to a diverse range of wildlife and ecosystems, and a growing number of eco-tourism initiatives are being developed in countries such as Ghana, Senegal, and Nigeria. These initiatives focus on sustainable tourism practices and conservation efforts (Emerald insight, 2019).

It is one thing for a country or region to be endowed with tourism potentials, it is another thing for that country or region to harness those potentials and positively project them for optimal benefits. Interestingly, opportunities in the tourism industry are endless and inexhaustible (WTTC, 2013). Unfortunately, many countries/regions of West African States in spite of their huge tourism potentials fail to succeed in ventures that fall within the purview of tourism (WTTC, 2013).

Travel and tourism in West African states is diverse and growing, characterized by key features:

- i. Cultural Heritage
- ii. Natural Attractions
- iii. Economic Impact
- iv. Challenges.
- v. Regional Initiatives
- vi. Growth Trends.
- vii. Overall, while travel and tourism in West African states face challenges, they hold significant potential for growth and development.

West African States Tourism Potential

West African States which comprises Benin, Burkina Faso, Cape Verde, Cote d'Ivoire, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea, Guinea-Bissau, Liberia, Mali, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Sierra Leone, and Togo, are each endowed with numerous tourist attractions ranging from physical to cultural, all of which are important for the region tourism development. They all have unique natural features, with cultural, historical, and religious resources and unique biodiversity; and great potential for tourism resources. These destinations are endowed with potential tourism resources (such as scenic landforms, mountains, gorges, unique biodiversity), and exceptional cultural and related resources (Nurhssen, 2016). West African States have great tourism potential due to their unique cultural heritage, pristine beaches, vibrant music and art scenes, and fascinating wildlife. (Nurhssen, 2016) and some of the most significant potentials for tourism in West African States include:

Nigeria: Nigeria have a year-round destinations and very rich in cultural heritage, which include wildlife parks (like Yankari), a vibrant festivals, as well as urban tourism in cities like Lagos, an area that has a rich cultural heritage, for example, Lekki Conservation Centre which has been running for about 23 year, situated in one of the most busiest and populated cities in Africa. Olumo Rock, which was believed to be a fortress for the inhabitants of the area during an old war located in Ogun State in the South-West of Nigeria, it boasts beautiful tourist spots and others such as Olumirin Waterfall in Erin-Ijesha, Ife Museum in Enuwa Square, the Olumo Rock, Agbokim Waterfall.

Ghana: Known for historical sites, including Cape Coast Castle, Kakum National Park, and its beautiful beaches, this ancient architecture is also called the Elmina Castle because it stands in a Ghanaian City called Elmina Vaugeous, (2010), it is amongst the oldest existing buildings in West Africa, having white-washed walls and this Castle tells the story of colonialism in Ghana were colonial masters conducted trade and the castle is a UNESCO World Heritage site. Hailed as West Africa's golden child, Ghana is an ideal destination with its authentic African culture, it's called 'Africa for beginners, there are beaches (like Labadie beach), luxury hotels and fascinating museums (Omoregie, 2019).

Mauritania: This site, Chinguetti, Mauritania a ksar located deep in the desert areas of Mauritania, it is an old town that has now been eroded and made not-so-inhabitable. Chinguetti was built in the 13th century which makes up a UNESCO World Heritage Site (WTTC (2013).

Senegal: Celebrated for its music and art scene, Dakar, the Goree Island UNESCO Site, and wildlife in Niokolo-Koba National Park. The Sine-Saloum Delta in Senegal is an area that consists of mangrove forests, islands, and lagoons including a ride to a spot from where pelicans can be spotted. Home to the *Monument de la Renaissance Africaine*. The African Renaissance Monument, which was built in 2010, is a statue expressing a rebirth of Africa and commemorating Senegalese independence, like many countries in West Africa, Senegal is also famous for its food. The Senegalese glean their culinary inspiration from far and wide, combining French and North African influences with ancient local traditions. The staple dish for most families is *thiéboudienne* (fish and rice). This is a small and very beautiful desert in Senegal, it stretches about 18 sq. km. The most beautiful thing about this desert, the very thing that has put it on this list of places to visit in West Africa, is the presence of orange sand dunes. These sand dunes are breath-taking in every possible way. If you are a lover of desserts, be here! You'll find it very thrilling.

Ivory Coast: Côte d'Ivoire has a network of 14 protected areas and specially developed hunting areas covering a total of over 2,500,000 Hecters and some of these protected areas are listed as World Heritage by UNESCO and the Ramsar Convention. Ivory Coast offers immense opportunities for photo safari tourism, sports hunting, sports fishing, beautiful beaches, cultural sites like Yamoussoukro Basilica, natural reserves and Taï National Park, which is one of the largest Catholic cathedrals in the world and stands in all its glory in the capital city of Ivory Coast, Yamoussoukro. This church can contain up to 18,000 congregants! The sight is simply breathtaking. Explore the oldest park in Lake Retba, is a red lake and is one of the fascinating sites in Africa and not just West Africa, but Africa as a whole. This lake is about 18 miles away from the capital city of Senegal. Tourists can watch the water, which changes color depending on the time of the day where animals can be viewed foraging in their natural habitats.

Mali: Home to the historic city of Timbuktu, UNESCO World Heritage sites, and a rich history of trade and culture. This is no doubt that the great Mosque of Djenné is one of the most astonishing religious buildings in West Africa and it stands in Djenné, a city in Mali. The Mosque is the product of an old but effective architectural design. It is made from brick and stands many feet tall.

Burkina Faso: Is known for its cultural festivals, natural beauty, and wildlife parks, for example, the Nazinga Game Ranch, the ruins of Loropeni, which are believed to be up to a thousand years old, is the first site in Burkina Faso, listed as a UNESCO World Heritage Site. The ruins of Loropeni tell a story of the gold trade across the Sahara. Burkina Faso boasts three impressive UNESCO World Heritage Sites. The Ruins of Loropéni, located near the borders of Côte d'Ivoire, Ghana and Togo, is nearly 1,000 years old. It is the best preserved of ten fortresses in the Lobi region dating back to the trans-Saharan gold trade. Another interesting sites is the Ancient Ferrous Metallurgy Sites dating back to the 8th century, which is the oldest surviving evidence of iron production in the country. The W-Arly-Pendjari Complex is a transnational property shared between Niger, Burkina Faso and the Republic of Benin, it encompasses terrestrial, semi-aquatic and aquatic ecosystems in the West African savanna belt. Burkina Faso is home to a famous mosque, built in 1893, the Grande Mosquée in Bobo-Dioulasso is one of the most exceptional examples of Sahel-style mud architecture in the region. It is made from mud-brick, projected wooden beams, horizontal beams and the complex also includes two minaret towers and a prayer hall.

Benin: Features historical sites like the Royal Palaces of Abomey and the vibrant voodoo culture. The Pendjari National Park is one of the biggest parks in West Africa, it lies in the North of the Benin Republic and spans up to 275,000 hectares, there are different forms of wildlife and vegetation, where a large number of elephants, African Buffalos, etc. are found and groomed; this park has once been

nominated to be enlisted in the UNESCO list of world heritage sites. Ganvie is a small village in the Benin Republic, surrounded by water, the village is, in fact, a wonder, where every building is built on water and is suspended in the air by large sticks that reach into the depths of the water.

Togo: Is where savannah dominates and the mysterious adobe villages of Koutammakou is found, it offers natural attractions, including beaches and hills, as well as cultural experiences in Lomé. Togo which has great touristic assets, including unique landscapes, globally-recognized monuments and sites, and a 45km coastline with beautiful fine sand beaches, Kpalime, Koutammakou, Lome, Togoville and Agbodrafo. The most enchanting place to visit in Togo is the UNESCO World Heritage site of Koutammakou at the Tamberma Valley. This location in the far north of the country and closer to Lome are the mystifying hills of the Kpalime region, which encompasses the tallest peak in the country. One of the most tranquil and most serene areas of Togo is the Kpalime region, a couple of hours' drive north of Lome, as you ascend the hills onto the plateau, one will be met with swarms of colorful butterflies while walking through the lush, green tropical rainforest. The area is surrounded by cocoa plantations, and one can climb the highest peak in the country, Mount Agou, for views of Lake Volta in neighboring Ghana and a Roman Catholic Church on top, which was built in 1913. In this valley you will find the Koutammakou UNESCO World Heritage site, which is home to the Batamamariba people, who live in houses constructed of mud-towers. Most of the buildings are two stories high, round, and have thatched straw roofs. Around the villages one can observe traditional farming being practiced.

Lake Togo: Lake Togo is a center of voodoo culture and there are several resorts around the lake where you can stay and learn more about this curious belief system. As one visit the area, you will see displays of voodoo 'fetishes' in the villages, and you can discover more by taking an organized guided tour. The lake itself offers plentiful boating opportunities to take it all. There are also two interesting museums in Lome: the National Museum of Togo and the International Museum of the Gulf of Guinea. This museum houses an impressive collection of African art, from traditional to more recent styles. There are also artifacts tracing the roots of the modern nation of Togo as well as musical instruments and textiles. A visit to Tamberma Villages in Togo shows the true African experience, its multi-story Grand Marché bazaar in Lomé (the capital). Tourists can sightsee the *Monument de l'Independance* and learn about the end of the colonial rule in Togo and the national museum, the food market and the Lomé Cathedral are a must-see as well.

Niger: Known for the Air Mountains, the Sahara Desert, and cultural tourism related to the Tuareg people. Zinder is the third-largest city in the Niger Republic. The city is a buzzing city characterized by a network of beautiful roads and an array of astonishing buildings. In this city, the Sultan's palace stands in its glory.

Chad: Offers unique desert landscapes, wildlife in Zakouma National Park, and cultural heritage.

Sierra Leone: Features beautiful beaches, historical sites, and ecotourism potential in its rainforests. Banana Island is one of the most visited places in Sierra Leone, it offers tourists the chance to engage in some of the most memorable experiences, one can engage in sports, fishing, scuba diving, watching whales and other water sports. Sierra Leone is endowed with tremendous touristic potentials with beautiful white and golden pristine beaches stretched several kilometers' along the peninsula, beautiful hotels and resorts for perfect relaxation. Sierra Leone has a vibrant tropical forest teeming with exotic wildlife and an excellent climate. From the Tacugama Chimpanzee Sanctuary, which provides a safe haven for Chimpanzees, the bountiful marine resources, sprawling hills and ranging Lion Mountains overlooking the cities, to Bunce Island, the cradle of the Trans-Atlantic Slaved. The country's six major

game parks and reserves have great opportunities for hunting, bird watching and ecotourism. And they include:

Dakar

Goree Island

Pink Lake

Senegal River

Petite Cote Beach

Gambia: The country is known for its hospitality, beaches, bird-watching opportunities, and cultural experiences, for example, Kotu Beach is one of the most relaxing, warmest places to visit in West Africa. The beach is located on the Atlantic coast of Gambia and the area welcomes a large number of tourists every year. Gambia has amazing reserves, such as Abuko National Reserve, Gambia National Park and Bijilo Forest Park, where various animals and rare species of wildlife are found. There are best hotels, restaurants and bars, surrounded by golden beaches backed by swaying palms sprinkled with scenic lagoons, an abundance of wildlife, vibrant history and culture, it offers visitors an opportunity to get in touch with nature.

Guinea: Beautiful landscapes, including mountainous regions and rich cultural traditions. This is one of the most beautiful places in Guinea and one of the most visited in West Africa.

Djallon Highlands sits in the heart of Guinea and comprises hills, valleys, and rocks. From a high point here, one can overlook waters including Gambia, Senegal, etc. The view is nothing short of aesthetic and calming. Bubaque Island is one of the islands that make up the Bijagós Islands in Guinea-Bissau. From here, one gets a view of the community, the waters, and the fishermen. The Bubaque Island Hotel, which stands on the Bubaque Island, is one of the most prominent hotels in the country.

Liberia: Offers historical attractions and ecotourism potential, especially in its national parks. Buchanan is a city in Liberia three hours away from Liberia's capital city and it is the third-largest city in Liberia and a welcome place for tourists. A visit here brings you face to face to what a beautiful coast life in West Africa looks like (Akomolafe, 2021).

Cape Verde: Fogo is an elevated island city in the small country of Cape Verde and the name Fogo translates to 'Fire.' The island stretches up to 476 sq. km. and reaches up to 2,829 meters tall. Fogo is called and with abundance of spectacular views and rich culture, each country's tourism potential is influenced by its cultural heritage, natural landscapes, wildlife, and historical significance. West African States have huge territory featuring beautiful countries with several hundred million inhabitants. These countries boast a rich history, beautiful scenery and friendly people.

Harnessing Tourism Potential in Advancing Promotion of Tourism in West African States

West African States has huge natural and cultural tourism resources with great potential to develop community-based ecotourism and these potentials include beautiful landscapes, unique wildlife and indigenous plant species, a clean and attractive natural environment, caves, waterfalls, escarpments and mountains; cultural tourism resource potentials are accompanied by other tangible and intangible cultural tourism resources (Avinor, 2020). Harnessing tourism potential in advancing the promotion of West Africa States requires a collaborative effort across the public and private sectors to develop a competitive and sustainable tourism industry that creates opportunities for economic growth and development in the region. The fourteen West African states can harness their tourism potential through a multifaceted approach through investing in transportation, accommodation, and essential services to improve accessibility and comfort for tourists. West Africa's States opportunity for harnessing their tourism potentials lies in several factors, which are its price competitiveness and

potential for nature tourism (Jenkins, 2015; Sharpley & Telfer, 2015). These opportunities encompasses in six categories in:

- i. Earning of foreign exchange
- ii. Revenue generation
- i. Employment opportunities.
- ii. Income generation.
- iii. Stimulus to inward investment and Regional development.

Challenges of Harnessing Tourism Potentials of West African sub-region

There are challenges that hindered harnessing tourism potentials of west African states and addressing this challenges is essential for the sustainable promotion of tourism in west African States, for example, some of the challenges include poor infrastructure, limited marketing and promotion etc these challenges require the west African states to needs to maximize tourism marketing and development through regional cooperation and the economic imbalances within the West African States integration processes should be looked into as wealthy countries are often more capable of profiting from tourism than less economically developed countries (Babatunde, 2006). The rich heritage of West Africa and its great natural beauty assets allow the development of various destinations products such as cultural and historical, costal or mountainous, sport or religious, thermal or gastronomic, business, and shopping tourism (Nigeria Tourism Development Corporation (NTDC, 2007). However despite the contribution tourism has on economic development in West Africa States, it has been limited by several challenges which according to Omoregie, (2019) includes:

- i. Poor infrastructure, including a lack of quality roads, airports, and reliable public transportation, can hinder the growth of tourism.
- ii. Political instability, terrorism, and crime remain major concerns in some West African countries, which make tourists hesitant to visit.
- iii. Lack of effective marketing strategies and promotional materials limit the visibility and awareness of West African tourist destinations in key markets.
- iv. Differences in language, values, customs, and traditions make it challenging for West African countries to attract and retain tourists from other parts of the world.
- v. Lack of adequate financial resources, which makes it difficult for many West African countries to invest in critical tourism infrastructure and marketing initiatives.
- vi. Pollution, deforestation, and other environmental challenges facing West African countries threaten the sustainability of tourism.
- vii. Seasonal workers employed by the industry often lack the necessary skills and do not enjoy fair working conditions, salaries and career opportunity.

Conclusion

It is now generally accepted that prerequisites for tourism development are attractions, accommodation and access, and without attractions either natural (climate, landscapes, coast, mountains) or man-made (historic sites, theme parks, festivals) tourism cannot develop. The combination of these attractions often put destinations on the tourism map. The paper concludes that:

More attention is being given now to public–private partnerships in which the government is building the infrastructure to facilitate the private sectors providing facilities for tourists and other users.

There is no market research to understand tourist preferences, allowing for tailored offerings and enhanced visitor experiences

Private sector do not invests in tourism through favorable investment conditions and tax incentives. Lack of organize and promotion of cultural, music, and art festivals to draw both domestic and international visitors.

Recommendations

The fourteen (14) countries that made up the West African States should combine their tourism potentials and seize this opportunity in promoting tourism, these requires a collaborative effort across the public and private sectors to develop a competitive and sustainable tourism industry that creates opportunities for economic growth and development in the region.

The paper therefore recommends that:

- i. West African states should muster political will and implement the existing legal framework to harness its tourism potential for economic development.
- ii. Investing in tourism infrastructure such as Accommodation (hotels), transportation, and entertainment facilities.
- iii. Ensuring the safety and security of tourists by developing safe and secure environments through appropriate security measures.
- iv. Encouraging private sector investment in tourism through favorable investment conditions and tax incentives.
- v. Highlight unique cultural assets, traditions, and festivals to attract interest and appreciation from tourists.
- vi. Foster partnerships among the states to create joint tourism packages and marketing strategies, promoting the region as a unified destination.
- vii. Implement initiatives that preserve natural and cultural resources, ensuring tourism benefits local communities while protecting the environment.
- viii. Develop targeted marketing campaigns that showcase the distinctive attractions of each country, leveraging digital platforms and social media.
- ix. Ensure a safe environment for tourists through improved security policies and crisis management plans, boosting traveler confidence.
- x. Provide incentives for private investment in tourism-related projects to stimulate growth in the sector.

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